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Research Article

**SCREENING OF IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF
ALCOHOLIC EXTRACT OF CINCHONA STEM BARK
EXTRACT**Syed Waseem^{1*}, Dr. Pawan Kumar², Dr. Parwez Alam³, Dr. Seema Firdouse⁴^{1,2} Department of Pharmaceutics, Singhania University, Pachheri bari, Jhunjhunu,
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Abstract:

Plants have a large number of bioactive compounds with high antioxidant activity. Studies for the determination of the antioxidant activity of different plant species could contribute to revealing the value of these species as a source of new antioxidant compounds. The aim of the present study were to evaluate in vitro antioxidant activities. The extract was prepared by using pure ethanol solvent for Cinchona officinalis stem bark. The in vitro antioxidant activity of Cinchona officinalis stem bark extract was evaluated by using different methods like nitric oxide scavenging activity, free radical scavenging by DPPH method and scavenging of hydroxyl radical (Deoxyribose Method). Vitamin-E was used as standard. The tested plant extract in different concentration showed promising antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity, Concentration 200 µg showed best antioxidant activity compared to other concentration in nitric oxide activity. In DPPH method Concentration 400µg showed maximum antioxidant activity compared to other concentration. From the obtained results we could suggest that this plant extract can be used for antioxidant activity.

Key words: Screening, In vitro antioxidant activity, Nitric oxide, DPPH, Deoxyribose method.**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Free radicals have been implicated in the causation of several problems like atherosclerosis, urolithiasis, ulcers, asthma, cancer, cardiovascular disease, cataract, diabetes, gastrointestinal inflammatory disease, liver disease, muscular degeneration and other inflammatory process. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are continuously produced during cell metabolism and under normal conditions; they are scavenged and converted to (Sen et al., 2010)[1]. Among these molecules, the compounds derived from secondary metabolism, specifically phenolic compounds, play a fundamental role against oxidative stress [2]. These compounds are known to act as antioxidants not only for their ability to donate hydrogen or electrons but also because they are stable radical intermediates [3]. Phenolic compounds also have protective effects on humans when the plants are consumed as food [3]. Generally, the antioxidant capacity of phenols in plant extracts is effective at low concentrations, and in humans, it is associated with the prevention of cardiovascular disease and cancer [4,5,6]. Thus, studies for the determination of the antioxidant activity of the extract of different plant species could contribute to establishing the value of these species as a source of new antioxidant compounds [7,8]. Nonreactive species by different intra cellular enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant system (Shao et al., 2008)[9]. Over production or an ineffective elimination of ROS may induce oxidative stress and cause damage to all types of bio molecules such as proteins, lipids and nucleic acids (Droge et al., 2011) [10]. Antioxidants may act as free radical scavengers, reducing agents, chelating agents for transition metals, quenchers of singlet oxygen molecules and or activators of antioxidative defense enzyme system to suppress the radical damages in biological systems (Mur et al., 2011; Venkatesh et al., 2009) [11,12]. Antioxidants thus play an important role in the protection of human body against damage by reactive oxygen species (Peng et al., 2011; Ling et al., 2011) [13,14]. The herb *Cinchona officinalis stem bark* contains compounds such as quinine, quinidine, cinchonine, cinchonidine, quinic acid, keno-tannic acid, qinovin, and kinova-tannic acid.

Due to presence of various active constituents in this plant an attempt has been made to evaluate the antioxidant property in various concentration of the plant extract, by *in vitro* antioxidant methods like Nitric oxide, DPPH, Deoxyribose method [15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**procurement of plant material:**

The crude drug *Cinchona officinalis stem bark* was procured from Yucca enterprises mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

Preparation of extract:

The procured plant material *Cinchona officinalis stem bark* were washed twice with tap water and one time with distilled water finally allowed to dry under shade, and then coarsely powdered in a blender. The coarse powder (250 gm) was subjected to maceration for 72 hours, followed by exhaustive maceration for 48 hours by using 99.9% ethanol for *Cinchona officinalis stem bark*. The solvents were decanted and filtered with filter paper and recovered by distillation at 60° C to 70° C. The extract was dried under desiccators [16].

METHODOLOGY:

The antioxidant activity of plant extract was proved by different In vitro methods which are given as follows -

- 1) Nitric oxide scavenging activity.
- 2) Free radical scavenging by DPPH method.
- 3) Scavenging of hydroxyl radical (deoxyribose method).

1) Nitric oxide scavenging activity procedure:

The nitric oxide scavenging activity of plant extract was determined according to the method (Green et al.,1982)[17]. Aqueous solution of sodium nitro prusside spontaneously generates nitric oxide (NO) at physiological pH, which interacts with oxygen to produce nitrate ions and which was measured colorimetrically. 3 ml of reaction mixture containing 2 ml of sodium nitro prusside (10 mM) in phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and 1ml of various concentrations of the extracts were incubated at 37°C for 4 hours. Control without test compound was kept in an identical manner. After incubation 0.5 ml of Griess reagent was added. The absorbance of the chromophore formed was read at 546nm. The percentage inhibition of nitric oxide generation was measured by comparing the absorbance values of control and those of test compounds. Vitamin-E (10, 50, 100, 200, 400, 800, 1000 µg/ml) was used as standard. The percentage nitric oxide inhibition was calculated from the following formula. The results were tabulated in table 1and represented in graph no.1.

$$\% \text{ Nitric Oxide Inhibition} = \frac{\text{OD of control} - \text{OD of test}}{\text{OD of control}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ DPPH Inhibition} = \frac{\text{OD of control} - \text{OD of test}}{\text{OD of control}} \times 100$$

2) Free radical scavenging by DPPH method procedure[18]:

DPPH scavenging activity was measured by the spectrophotometric method. A stock solution of 25 mg of DPPH (150 μM) was prepared in 100 mL of ethanol. To the 0.2 ml of extract of different concentrations, 3.8 ml of DPPH was added. Control without test compound was prepared in an identical manner. In case of blank, DPPH was replaced by ethanol. The reaction was allowed to be completed in the dark for about 20 minutes. Then the absorbance of test mixtures was read at 517 nm. The percentage inhibition was calculated and expressed as percent scavenging of DPPH radical. Vitamin-E (10, 50, 100, 200, 400, 800, 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was used as standard. The percentage DPPH inhibition was calculated from the following formula. The results are tabulated in table 2 and represented in graph no. 2.

3) Scavenging of hydroxyl radical (deoxyribose method) procedure [19]:

To the reaction mixture containing deoxy ribose (3mM, 0.2ml), ferric chloride (0.1mM,0.2ml), Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid sodium salt (EDTA) (0.1 mM, 0.2 ml), ascorbic acid (0.1 mM, 0.2 ml), and hydrogen peroxide (2 mM, 0.2 mM) in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4,20 mM), was added to 0.2 ml various concentrations of extracts or standard in DMSO to give a total volume 1.2 ml. the solutions were then incubated for 30 min at 37°C. After incubation, trichloro acetic acid (0.2ml,15%), and thio barbituric acid (0.2 ml, 1% w/v) in 0.25 N HCl were added. The reaction mixture was kept in a boiling water bath for 30 minute, cooled, and the absorbance was measured at 532 nm. The results are tabulated in Table no. 3 and represented in Graph no. 3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

1) Percentage inhibition by nitric oxide method:

Sample No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% inhibition
plant ext.		
1.	10 μg	39.36
2.	50 μg	47.15
3.	100 μg	53.41
4.	200 μg	59.11
5.	400 μg	54.74
6.	800 μg	52.58
7.	1000 μg	53.48
Standard Vit.E		
8.	10 μg	43.0
9.	50 μg	53.7
10.	100 μg	57.8
11.	200 μg	66.1
12.	400 μg	75.2
13.	800 μg	78.5
14.	1000 μg	93.3

Table No. 1: Percentage inhibition by nitric oxide method.

Figure 1: Nitric oxide percentage inhibition graph.

Discussion:

In the present study plant extract at different concentration were assessed for their free radical scavenging activity in an in vitro nitric oxide model. It was observed that % inhibition of plant extract scavenged free radical in a dose dependent manner. All the concentration showed significant increased or decreased in the nitric oxide percent inhibition. So the plant extract under investigation are potent inhibitor of nitric oxide.

2) Effect of different concentration of extract on DPPH percentage inhibition:

Sample No.	Concentration(µg/ml)	% inhibition
plant ext.		
1.	10µg	34.52
2.	50µg	49.32
3.	100µg	59.89
4.	200µg	80.44
5.	400µg	91.35
6.	800µg	89.26
7.	1000µg	81.86
Standard Vit.E		
8.	10µg	49.66
9.	50µg	62.25
10.	100µg	73.68
11.	200µg	83.87
12.	400µg	92.44
13.	800µg	94.69
14.	1000µg	97.87

Table No. 2: Percentage inhibition by DPPH method.

Figure 2: DPPH percentage inhibition graph

Discussion:

In the present study plant extract at different concentration were assessed for their free radical scavenging activity in an in vitro DPPH model. All the concentration showed change in the DPPH percent inhibition. It was observed that % inhibition of plant extract scavenged free radical in a dose dependent manner. All the concentration showed significant increased in the DPPH percent inhibition. So the plant extract under investigation are potent inhibitor of free radical.

3) Effect of different ratios of extracts on Hydroxyl radical percentage inhibition:

Sample No.	Concentration(µg/ml)	% inhibition
plant ext.		
1.	10µg	30.64
2.	50µg	32.31
3.	100µg	35.44
4.	200µg	51.84
5.	400µg	62.47
6.	800µg	69.65
7.	1000µg	80.41
Standard Vit.E		
8.	10µg	35.33
9.	50µg	40.50
10.	100µg	61.11
11.	200µg	69.41
12.	400µg	79.61
13.	800µg	86.30
14.	1000µg	97.72

Table No. 3: Percentage inhibition by hydroxyl radical method.

Figure 3: Hydroxyl radical percentage inhibition graph

DISCUSSION:

In the present study plant extract at different concentration were assessed for their free radical scavenging activity in an in vitro hydroxyl radical method. All the concentration showed change in the percent inhibition. It was observed that % inhibition of plant extract scavenged free radical in a dose dependent manner. All the concentration showed significant increased in the Hydroxyl radical percentage inhibition in graph according to concentration. So the plant extract under investigation are potent inhibitor of free radical.

CONCLUSION:

The in-vitro antioxidant activity of plant extract results were clearly indicated in tabular column. That all the concentration of extract in different models was effective in scavenging free radicals and has the potential to be a powerful antioxidant activity.

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